

Determining the Tools of Teaching the English Language through the Application of Analytic Hierarchy Process (AHP)

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Article Info	Abstract
<p><i>Article History</i></p> <p>Received: April 19, 2021</p> <p>Accepted: September 27, 2021</p> <hr/> <p>Keywords : Teaching the English Language, Application, Analytic Hierarchy Process</p> <p>DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.5532881</p>	<p><i>The process of determining the appropriate teaching aids is an important pillar for the success of the educational process of the English language or other teaching materials. Therefore, deciding to select the appropriate educational medium is the first step to the success of education. This study aims to determine the available options for using them as teaching aids, in addition to identifying the challenges facing the application of these aids. To achieve these goals, the previous literature was referred to and the study methodology was determined in terms of data collection and analysis through interviews, and then extracting the available Tools, in addition to making a comparison among the options, and deriving the order of priorities for the Tools using Analytic Hierarchy Process (AHP).</i></p>

Introduction

The quality of education is based on the learning environment that includes, the student, the teacher, the scientific content, and the teaching aids (Ahmed et al., 2018; Mulang 2021). This environment needs continuous development to ensure the quality of education. The success of education is an integrated process among these four main components. The previous studies indicate the importance of the quality of education and the measures of this quality through various studies in the areas of performance, factors affecting the performance of the student or teacher, in addition to studies aimed at developing educational content and studies aimed at developing educational aids, and research in these topics needs to keep pace with continuous updating to ensure the improvement of the process Education in an integrated way. Despite the importance of the educational materials as a whole, the English language is one of the most important educational materials because it is widespread and important for the study of other sciences (Zarei et al., 2021). Therefore, the development of students' competence in the English language is a goal that most educational institutions seek at the level of school and university education, from this point of view comes the importance of paying attention to developing the process of teaching the English language in its four axes, the student, the teacher, the educational content, and the teaching aids. Despite the importance of developing the four educational axes (Muhamadjonovna, 2020). This study will be limited to teaching aids specifically.

This study comes in light of the need to identify the most important educational Tools available for teaching English in schools, and then determine the priorities among these Tools, and identify the challenges facing the process of applying the Tools. In light of this, the study will include five main sections. The introduction in the first section, which highlights the importance of the study, the previous studies in the second section, which include studies in the field of education and teaching aids, and then the methodology of the study in the third section, which includes the steps of applying the study, while the fourth section includes the process of analysis of data and results, and finally the discussion in the fifth section .

2. Literature Rearview

2.1 English Language and Teaching Aids

There are many studies that are concerned with the process of developing education for the English language, some of these studies rely on multiple methodologies, including:

- Studies aiming to develop new tools for teaching English using modern methods (Xodabande, 2017; Kessler, 2018; Klimova, 2018). These studies are carried out through the application of the teaching method and making analytical comparisons to measure effectiveness. Through the literature of

previous studies on the subject of teaching aids for the English language, it is clear that there is a diversity of Tools, which include: Phone, games, digital classroom interactions, educational videos, social sites, chatting, personal computers, smart applications (Jabbarova, 2020; Poláková et al., 2021).

- Studying the effectiveness of teaching aids for the English language by making comparisons between the experimental group and the control groups (Ta'amneh, 2020; Magableh & Abdullah, 2020). During this type of studies, training is conducted for the experimental group and pre- and post-training tests are conducted.

- Surveys of opinions about the process of learning English (Kim, 2020 Kazu & Issaku, 2020). This type of studies aims to measure satisfaction or extract impact or effectiveness, and is done through the design of questionnaires.

- Evaluation studies are carried out through direct tests and comparison of results. These studies come with the aim of measuring effectiveness, performance, efficiency and soliciting opinions (Pinto-Llorente, 2020).

The previous literature indicates a subtle diversity of studies related to the English language, some in the Tools of reading, some in the Tools of listening, some in the vocabulary, and some in the grammar. This diversity indicates that the study in the Tools of teaching the English language needs continuous updating due to the continuous development of the Tools.

2.1 Analytic Hierarchy Process (AHP)

The hierarchical analysis method is considered one of the best analytical methods among a group of available options, and it is used in wide applications for decision-making, it is used in engineering, commercial, and educational applications, It is used as a scientific methodology in setting strategies, setting standards, and setting priorities (Li, 2017; Yulmaini et al., 2018; Arora et al., 2020).

3. Methodology

3.1 Main Steps of the Methodology

To achieve the main objectives of the study, the following steps were taken:

1. The first step: identifying the study sample with experts and supervisors of teaching English in the Jordanian Ministry of Education.
2. Second Step: The main question of the personal interview has been determined, which includes:

What are the Tools available to teach English in public schools?

What are the factors affecting the application of these Tools.

What are the challenges facing the process of applying these methods.

3. The third step: Conducting interviews to determine the available teaching methods for learning English and the challenges and obstacles facing these Tools.
4. The fourth step: the application of the hierarchical analysis to compare between the Tools, where the steps were applied according to the following figure 3.1.

Figure 3.1 Outline of the Steps for Applying AHP

3.2 Applied Procedures

The implementation procedures of the previous steps included the following:

1. Interviews were conducted on a sample of 17 experts in the field of English language education.
2. The texts were collected and the texts analyzed for the answers to the three questions using a program NVivo where it helps qualitative researchers to organize, analyze and find insights in unstructured or qualitative data like interviews, open-ended survey responses, journal articles, social media and web content, where deep levels of analysis on small or large volumes of data are required

The answers include the following main teaching aids:

- Most of the answers, and 90%, included a reference to direct instruction as a primary Tools of learning English.
- Most of the answers, with 80%, included a reference to the use of e-learning as a Tools of learning the English language.
- The responses included a 75% reference to blended learning as an effective Tools of learning English, and more than 60% of the responses included a reference to the use of educational videos and the use of games.

Through the answers, the Tools were categorized into:

1. Direct education.
2. E-learning.
3. Blended education.

While the factors and criteria affecting the application of these methods included the following:

1. Infrastructure.
2. Training.
3. Cost.
4. Efficiency.

3.3 Data Collection for AHP Structure

In the light of the results obtained from the achievement of the first and second objectives, it is possible to identify the basic elements for the implementation of the hierarchical analysis, since the results of the first and second objectives include:

1. Identifying the alternatives available for education in the light of the first equation.
2. Determining the criteria and factors affecting the alternatives available for education in the light of the second equation.
3. Building on the hierarchical structure of the evaluation process among alternatives.
4. Designing a data collection method and comparing alternatives, taking into account the effect of criteria and influences.
5. Data collection by personal interviews and the data collection tool.
6. Analyzing the data using a sequence of calculations to calculate the weights of the alternatives.

4. Results and Discussion

The main findings of this study included the following:

4.1 AHP Structure

Through the data obtained after analyzing the texts for the answers, the hierarchical structure was developed as in the following Figure 3.2.

4.2 Comparison Tables and Data Collection

Through the hierarchical structure, comparison tables are designed as follows:

4.1 Comparison of Criteria

Criteria	Criteria	Most influential	Main Degree 1-9
Infrastructure	Training	Training	5
Infrastructure	Cost	Infrastructure	1
Infrastructure	Efficiency	Efficiency	7
Training	Cost	Training	3
Training	Efficiency	Efficiency	3
Cost	Efficiency	Efficiency	3

The above Table 4.1 refers to data collected from experts for comparison and prioritization of criteria, these data according to the hierarchical analysis can be written according to the following Table 4.2.

Table 4.2 Analytic Hierarchy Process of Criteria

Criteria	I	T	C	E	AHP Analysis	
Infrastructure (I)	1	1/5	1	1/7		
Training (T)	5	1	3	1/3		
Cost (C)	1	1/3	1	1/3		
Efficiency (E)	7	3	3	1		
Total of Column (TC)	T1= 14	T2= 4.53	T3= 8.00	T4=1.80	Total of Raw	Average of Raw
I/TC	0.07	0.05	0.125	0.08	0.325	0.08
T/TC	0.36	0.22	0.375	0.18	1.14	0.29
C/TC	0.07	0.07	0.125	0.18	0.45	0.11
E/TC	0.50	0.66	0.375	0.56	2.1	0.52

From the previous Table 4.2, it is noticeable that the order of the criteria are as follows:

1. Efficiency with a weight of 52%.

2. **Training with a weight 29%.**
3. **Cost with a weight 11%.**
4. **Infrastructure with a weight 8%.**

The results in the previous Table indicate that efficiency is the main criterion in determining education priorities in light of the available alternatives. This reference is consistent with the educational goals that seek to achieve high quality in educational outcomes.

4.3 Comparison of the Tools According to the Infrastructure Variable

Tools	Tools	Most influential	Degree 1-9
Direct education	E-learning	E-learning	3
Direct education	Blended education	Blended education	5
E-learning	Blended education	Blended education	7

The above Table 4.3 refers to data collected from experts for comparison and prioritization of criteria, these data according to the hierarchical analysis can be written according to the following Table 4.4

4.4. Analytic Hierarchy Process of the Tools According to the Infrastructure Variable

Tools	DE	EL	BE	AHP Analysis	
Direct education (DE)	1	1/3	1/5		
E-learning (EL)	3	1	1/7		
Blended education (BE)	5	7	1		
Total of Column (TC)	T1= 9.00	T2= 8.33	T3= 1.34	Total of Raw	Average of Raw
DE/TC	0.12	0.04	0.15	0.31	0.10
EL/TC	0.33	0.12	0.10	0.55	0.18
BE/TC	0.55	0.84	0.75	2.14	0.72

From the previous Table 4.4, it is noticeable that the order of the Tools According to the Infrastructure Variable are as follows:

1. **Blended education with a weight of 72%.**
2. **E-learning with a weight 18%.**
3. **Direct education with a weight 10%.**

The results in the previous Table 4.4 indicate that blended education comes first in terms of available alternatives in light of being affected by the infrastructure criterion. This reference is consistent with the need to provide the necessary infrastructure for the application of blended education.

4.5 Comparison of the Tools According to Training Variable

Tools	Tools	Most influential	Degree 1-9
Direct education	E-learning	E-learning	7
Direct education	Blended education	Blended education	5
E-learning	Blended education	E-learning	3

4.6. Analytic Hierarchy Process of the Tools According to the Training Variable

Tools	DE	EL	BE	AHP Analysis	
Direct education (DE)	1	1/7	1/5		
E-learning (EL)	7	1	3		
Blended education (BE)	5	1/3	1		
Total of Column (TC)	T1= 13	T1= 1.47	T3= 4.2	Total of Raw	Average of Raw
DE/TC	0.08	0.09	0.05	0.22	0.08
EL/TC	0.54	0.68	0.71	1.93	0.64
BE/TC	0.38	0.23	0.24	0.85	0.28

From the previous Table 4.6, it is noticeable that the order of the Tools According to the Infrastructure Variable are as follows:

1. **E-learning with a weight of 64%.**
2. **Blended education with a weight 28%.**
3. **Direct education with a weight 8%.**

The results in the previous Table 4.6 indicate that E-learning comes in the first place in terms of available alternatives in light of being affected by the training criterion. This reference is consistent with the need to provide training for teachers to ensure the successful implementation of the transition to E-learning.

4.7 Comparison of the Tools According to Cost Variable

Tools	Tools	Most influential	Degree 1-9
Direct education	E-learning	E-learning	5
Direct education	Blended education	Blended education	7
E-learning	Blended education	Blended education	3

4.8 Analytic Hierarchy Process of the Tools According to the Cost Variable

Tools	DE	EL	BE	AHP Analysis	
Direct education (DE)	1	1/5	1/7		
E-learning (EL)	5	1	3		
Blended education (BE)	7	1/3	1		
Total of Column (TC)	T1= 13	T2= 1.47	T3= 4.14	Total of Raw	Average of Raw
DE/TC	0.08	0.23	0.04	0.35	0.12
EL/TC	0.38	0.68	0.72	1.78	0.59
BE/TC	0.54	0.09	0.24	0.87	0.29

From the previous Table 4.8, it is noticeable that the order of the Tools According to the Cost Variable are as follows:

1. E-learning with a weight of 59%.
2. Blended education with a weight 29%.
3. Direct education with a weight 12%.

The results in the previous Table 4.8 indicate that e-learning is ranked first in terms of available alternatives in light of being affected by the cost criterion, as the cost is reduced due to the abandonment of teachers and huge school buildings, and the cost becomes less, as the limits of classroom absorption increase through e-learning.

4.9 Comparison of the Tools According to Efficiency Variable

Tools	Tools	Most influential	Degree 1-9
Direct education	E-learning	E-learning	3
Direct education	Blended education	Blended education	5
E-learning	Blended education	Blended education	3

4.10 Analytic Hierarchy Process of the Tools According to the Efficiency Variable

Tools	DE	EL	BE	AHP Analysis	
Direct education (DE)	1	1/3	1/5		
E-learning (EL)	3	1	1/3		
Blended education (BE)	5	3	1		
Total of Column (TC)	T1= 9	T2= 4.33	T3= 1.53	Total of Raw	Average of Raw
DE/TC	0.11	0.08	0.14	0.33	0.11
EL/TC	0.33	0.23	0.20	0.76	0.26
BE/TC	0.55	0.69	0.66	1.90	0.63

From the previous Table 4.10, it is noticeable that the order of the Tools According to the Efficiency Variable are as follows:

1. Blended education with a weight 63%.
2. E-learning with a weight of 26%.
3. Direct education with a weight 11%.

The results indicate that blended learning advances priorities under the influence of the competency criterion, and this result reinforces the importance of blended learning.

4.3 Compare Priorities

In order to compare the previous results, in this step, the criteria will be merged into the matrix A, then merge the priorities into the matrix B, then perform matrix multiplication.

Matrix A =	0.08			
	0.29			
	0.11			
	0.52			
Matrix B =	0.10	0.08	0.12	0.11
	0.18	0.64	0.59	0.26
Matrix B X	0.72	0.28	0.25	0.11
		DE	0.11	0.63
		EL	0.40	
		BE	0.49	

In the final result, it appears that blended education comes first in terms of priorities with a percentage of 49%, then e-learning by 40%, while direct education comes in the last place with a rate of 11%.

These results indicate that the blended education is the best choice for education according to the opinion of experts and within the influential standards. While the challenges were based on the availability of infrastructure such as the Internet, the availability of computers for students, the availability of training on the use of modern educational Tools, in addition to challenges related to the slow implementation of the implementation procedures for the transition to blended education.

5. Conclusion

The main results showed that there are three main educational options: traditional education, e-learning, and blended education. The results showed that the hierarchical analysis method is effective in setting priorities, as the results of the hierarchical analysis showed that blended education is the best option, while the challenges are related to infrastructure and training. Despite the different criteria affecting the decision, blended education was the most important priority in all comparisons.

In light of these results, there is a need to pay attention to the infrastructure of the blended education transformation process to ensure the quality and continuity of education, and there is a need to provide blended learning methods for students in schools or homes, and this constitutes an economic challenge to the blended education transformation process.

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